

STUDY OF PUMPING METHODS IN EDFA AND ITS APPLICATION FOR 16 CHANNEL EDFA-WDM SYSTEM

Abdul Khaliq

Research Scholar

M.Tech 4th Semester,

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering
Al-Falah University, Dhauj, Faridabad, Haryana

Prof. Ravinder Kumar

Assistant professor,

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering
Al-Falah University, Dhauj, Faridabad, Haryana

ABSTRACT

Gain and noise figure are two important parameter of EDFA. The gain flatness of EDFA is always desirable in DWDM system application in all optical network design. The objective of the thesis is to study EDFA and its application in 16 channels WDM system. In the first part, various EDFA pumping schemes are studied and analysed. The analysis is made for high pump power of 200 to 600 mW. Standard erbium doped fiber of length 16.2m is used. Input signal power is set at -34dBm at 1550 nm. Output power calculated is in the range of 15-25dBm, while the noise figure varied between 4.37-7.24dBm. Among the different pumping method bi-directional one has been found to have best performance. In the second part, a 16 channel EDFA-WDM system is designed and analysed in C-band wavelengths between 1548 to 1560 nm. To achieve gain flatness of EDFA, analysis has been carried out by varying pump power between 100 to 400 mW and input signal power between -20 to -35dBm. The gains are flattened within 38.7 ± 1.37 dB for wavelength range 1548 nm to 1560 nm using optimized EDFA of length 10m. The working model consist of WDM transmitter, 16 channels MUX, dual port WDM analyzer, 980 nm pump laser and optimized EDFA as key components. The system layouts and analysis, in both the sections are made using Optisystem software.

Key words: EDFA-WDM SYSTEM, C-band wavelengths, WDM transmitter, Optisystem software

INTRODUCTION

Optical communication systems use electronic regenerators for amplifying the optical signals. Earlier in long distance communication system, attenuated optical signal is amplified electronically using regenerative repeater, by first converting optical signal into electrical domain and then converting back to the optical domain. Such regenerators are designed to operate at one optical wavelength and specific bit rate. In wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) systems carrying multiple wavelength signals through one fiber, the electronic regeneration would be very complex and expensive. Optical amplifier like erbium doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) can amplify the incoming optical signals in the optical domain itself without any conversions to the electrical domain. It does not require any high speed electronic circuitry

and it is transparent to bit rate and it can amplify multiple optical signals at different wavelength simultaneously.

The development of EDFA provide tremendous growth in communication system capacity using WDM, in which multiple wavelengths carrying independent high bit rate signals are simultaneously propagated through same single mode fiber. Optical amplifiers can be used at many points in communication link. A booster amplifier is used to boost the power of the transmit signal before it launching into the fiber link. The pre amplifier placed just before the receiver is used to increase the receiver sensitivity. In-line amplifiers are used at intermediate points in the fiber link to overcome losses. Today, most of the optical fiber communication system use EDFAs, due to their advantages in terms of bandwidth, high power output, and low noise characteristics. Erbium doped fiber amplifier is an optical amplifier, it amplifies weak input optical signals directly without any conversions pumped with a laser diode.

The main application of EDFA is to amplify signals in optical domain. The EDFA became a key enabling technology for optical communication networks, and have since comprised the vast majority of all optical amplifiers deployed in almost all optical fiber networks. Erbium doped fiber amplifier is most common optical amplifier, commercially available since the early 1990's. It is a most stable optical amplifier supporting large number of channels in WDM system, especially in c-band (1525 to 1565 nm) [1-2] wavelength region. The important characteristics of EDFA are efficient pumping, high gain and low noise. However, EDFA gains are widely wavelength dependent and needs gain flattening for dense wavelength division multiplexing (DWDM) system involving large number of channels with channel spacing of the order of 0.5 nm or even lower.

Several methods exist for EDFA gain flattening [3-4]. By using several high pump powers or by changing erbium doped fiber length or by varying input power one can achieve flat gains [5-8]. One can also achieve it by properly choosing optical notch filter characteristics [9]. In this work, the EDFA gain flattening is achieved by variation of pump power and input power for optimized erbium doped fiber length using optisystem.

NEED OF OPTICAL AMPLIFIER

The transmission distance of any fiber optic communication system is eventually limited by fiber losses for long haul system the loss limitation has traditionally been overcome using opto-electronic repeaters in which the optical signal is first converted into an electric current and then regenerated using transmitter such regenerator become quite complex and expensive for wavelength division multiplexed light wave system. An alternative approach to loss management makes use of optical amplifiers, which amplify the optical signal directly without requiring its conversion to the electric domain.

Several kinds of optical amplifiers were most optical amplifiers amplify incident light through stimulated emission, the same mechanism that is used by lasers. Indeed, an optical amplifier is nothing but a laser without feedback. Its main ingredient is the *optical gain* realized when the amplifier is pumped (optically or electrically) to achieve *population inversion*. The optical gain, in general, depends not only on the frequency (or wavelength) of the incident signal, but also on the local beam intensity at any point inside the amplifier. Details of the frequency and intensity dependence of the optical gain depend on the

amplifier medium, which is modelled as a homogeneously broadened two-level system and analyze using rate equations. Optical amplifiers are important in optical communication and laser physics.

Optical amplifiers are used extensively in fiber optic data links. Fig.1.1 shows three ways in which optical amplifiers can be used to enhance the performance of optical data links. A booster amplifier is used to increase the optical output of an optical transmitter just before the signal enters an optical fiber. The optical signal is attenuated as it travels in the optical fiber. An in-line amplifier is used to restore (regenerate) the optical signal to its original power level. An optical pre-amplifier is used at the end of the optical fiber link in order to increase the sensitivity of an optical receiver. These amplifiers should have specific characteristics for specific amplifications.

Fig. 1 Optical Amplifier in a fiber optic data link

TYPES OF AMPLIFIERS

A brief description of the different types of optical amplifiers is presented here. Following three types of optical amplifiers are useful.

- i) Semiconductor Optical Amplifiers (SOAs)
- ii) Fiber Raman Amplifiers
- iii) Rare earth doped fiber amplifiers (Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifiers-EDFA, Praseodymium Doped Fiber Amplifiers-PDFA)

Semiconductor Optical Amplifiers (SOA)

All lasers act as amplifiers close to but before reaching threshold, and semiconductor lasers are no exception. Indeed, research on semiconductor optical amplifiers (SOAs) started soon after the invention of semiconductor lasers in 1962. However it was only during the 1980s that SOAs were developed for practical applications, motivated largely by their potential applications in light wave systems[10].

Fig. 2 Semiconductor optical amplifier

A semiconductor optical amplifier is shown in Fig.2. The gain medium is undoped InGaAsP. This material can be tailored to provide optical amplification at wavelengths near 1.3 μm or near 1.5 μm – important wavelengths for optical communications. Other semiconductors can be used to amplify optical signals at other wavelengths. The input and output faces of the amplifier are antireflection coated in order to prevent optical feedback to the gain medium and lasing. In semiconductor optical amplifier electrical current is used as pumping signal

The basic structure of the SOA is a semiconductor laser composed of an optical waveguide between a P-N junction with an input and output coated facets as displayed in Fig. 3 [11]. When a direct current (DC) is biased to the SOA, electrons get higher energy. Hence, the conduction and valence bands (energy levels) containing electrons and holes, respectively are formed [12]. The formation of these energy levels results in three radiative mechanisms within the SOA: (i) Spontaneous emission: which is the process where an electron from the conduction band drops to the valence band releasing a photon or generating heat. This process is considered as loss or noise because the generated photon is radiated with different phase and direction.

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of SOA

(ii) Stimulated absorption: this is the process by which an electron in the valence band absorbs enough energy from an incident photon to pass the energy gap to the conduction band and hence causes loss. (iii) Stimulated emission; this process occurs when an incoming optical beam is launched into the active waveguide of the SOA via the input facet of the amplifier, an incident photon collides with an excited

electron from the conduction band releasing a stimulated photon with the same phase, frequency and direction (i.e. amplification takes place). More identical photons are released by the collision of the incident beam of photons with more excited electrons in the conduction band thus amplifying the input signal [1]. The reduction of excited electrons in the conduction band (i.e. the carrier density) will result in a decrease in the SOA gain because the gain is proportional to the carrier population.

Moreover, it will increase the active refractive index due to the nonlinear refractive index being dependent on the carrier density. When a short input optical pulse is launched into the SOA, stimulation emission will take place resulting in signal amplification. Therefore, the carrier density will be reduced and will cause a drop in the SOA gain. The carrier non-equilibrium is governed mainly by the spectral hole burning effect. The distribution recovers to equilibrium by carrier-carrier scattering. Instantaneous mechanisms such as two-photon absorption and the optical Kerr effects will then influence on the SOA response. After few picoseconds, a quasi-equilibrium distribution will occur due to the carrier temperature relaxation process and then the carrier density will be recovered.

There are two types of SOAs:

- (a) Fabry –Perot amplifiers (FPA)
- (b) Non resonant travelling wave amplifiers (TWA)

(a) Fabry-Perot amplifier

When the light enters FPA it gets amplified as it reflects back and forth between the mirrors until emitted at a higher intensity shown in Fig 4. It is sensitive to temperature and input optical frequency.

Fig. 4 An Fabry-Perot amplifier (FPA)

Fig. 5A

travelling wave amplifier

(b) Travelling Wave amplifier

It is the same as FPA except that the end facets are either antireflection coated or cleaved at an angle so that internal reflection does not take place and the input signal gets amplified only once during a single pass through the device as shown in Fig. 5 They are widely used because they have a large optical bandwidth, and low polarization sensitivity.

Fibre Raman Optical Amplifier

The gain medium is undoped optical fiber. Power is transferred to the optical signal by a nonlinear optical process known as the Raman effect. Power to supply the optical gain is supplied by an optical pump. The wavelengths that experience optical gain are determined by the wavelength of the optical pump, so the Raman amplifier can be tailored to amplify a given optical wavelength by proper selection of the pump wavelength.

Fig. 6: A Fiber Raman Amplifier

The optical gain in a Raman amplifier is distributed over a long span of optical fiber. Typically, the optical pump is introduced at the end of a length of fiber in order to provide optical gain that increases towards the end of the fiber. In this way, a Raman amplifier can be combined with an EDFA booster or in-line amplifier to produce a more uniform power profile along the length of fiber which is shown in Fig. 6.

Erbium Doped Fibre Amplifiers(EDFA)

Erbium is generally preferred in fiber for amplification because of the inherent properties associated with it. Erbium ions have quantum levels that can be stimulated to emit in 1550nm band with least power loss. Moreover the property of erbium is that its quantum levels allow it to get excited by 980nm or 1480 nm pump signals. The amplification is achieved by stimulated emission of photons from erbium ions in the doped fiber. The pump laser excites erbium ions into a higher energy from ground level. The ions in the higher energy level will soon decay spontaneously very fast to the meta-stable level, the life time of erbium ions in this level is higher (~10ms).The erbium is pumped to a state of population inversion with a separate optical input as shown in Fig. 6.

When the erbium is illuminated with light energy at a suitable wavelength (either 980nm or 1480nm) it is excited to a long lifetime intermediate state as shown in Fig. 8, following which it decays back to the ground state by emitting light in the wavelength range of 1525-1565nm, the optical wavelengths that suffer minimum attenuation in optical fiber, making the EDFA as amplifier in WDM applications.

Fig. 7 Erbium Doped Fibre Amplifier

Fig. 8Erbium ion transition

EDFA PUMPING SCHEMES

Three pumping techniques namely co-directional pumping, counter pumping, and bidirectional pumping are useful in EDFA [19-20].

Co-Directional Pumping

In co-directional pumping, both input signal and pump signal travel in the same direction inside the optical fiber. A combiner i.e., wavelength division multiplexer is used to combine both input signal and pump signal. The pump signal transfers its energy to input signal and the information carrying signal gets amplified at the output of the fiber. Isolators are also used to ensure that signal travel only in forward direction and are not reflected backward. Fig. 9 shows the basic principle of co-direction pumping laser.

Fig. 9 Co-directional pumping

Counter-Directional Pumping

In counter pumping scheme, the input signal and the pump signal travel in opposite direction inside the optical fiber. In backward pumping, the direction of the signal is insignificant. The information carrying signal gets amplified while travelling in opposite direction. Fig. 10 describes the principle of counter pumping laser.

Fig. 10 Counter-directional pumping

Bi-Directional Pumping

In bidirectional pumping, the input signal travels in the forward direction. But in bidirectional pumping, two pump laser are used which travel in both forward and backward direction inside the fiber along with the input signal. Fig. 11 describes the principle of bidirectional pumping.

Fig. 11 Bi-directional pumping

Investigation On Pumping Methods

The layouts for analysing three different pumping mechanisms are shown in Fig 12, 13 and 14 respectively. The layouts mainly consist of CW laser source for input signal at 1550 nm, pump laser source at 980 and 1480 nm, erbium doped fiber amplifier, dual port WDM analyser, optical spectrum analyzer and optical power meter. Table 1 shows the used parameters for different system components. High amplifier gains in the range 39-46 dB can be obtained by sweeping the pump power from 200 mW to 600 mW. The signal input power considered is -34dBm at 1550 nm wavelength. Output power calculated in this project is in the range 15 to 25dBm, while the noise figure varied between 4.37 to 7.24dBm. Different signal input power or signal wavelength as well as fiber parameters can also be simulated to obtained new results and can be compared.

Table 1 System parameters for EDFA pumping study

Components	Parameters	Values
CW laser	Input power	-34 dBm
	Wavelength	1550 nm
Pump lasers	Pump powers	200, 300, 400, 500 and 600 mW
	Wavelengths	980 nm, 1480 nm
EDF	Length	16.2 m
	Er ion density	$10 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$
	Er metastable time	10 ms
	Core radius	1.3 μm
	NA	0.27

Fig. 12 Layout in co-propagating scheme

Fig. 13 Layout in counter-propagating scheme

Fig. 14 Layout in bi-directional pumping scheme

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 respectively show the gain and noise figure (NF) variation with pumping powers for co-propagating pumping at 980 nm. As seen from these figures that the both gains and NF are slowly increasing with increase in pump powers. The gain of the amplifier varies between 39.62 to 43.18 dB and the NF varies between 4.37 to 4.39 dB. The output signal levels are low and varies between 14.85 to 19.99 dB. Table 2 shows the results.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 15 (a) Gain and (b) Noise Figure variation for Co-propagating pumping @980 nm

Table 2: Gain, noise figure and output power for co-propagating pumping @980 nm

Pump Powers (mw)	Gains (dB)	Noise Figures (dB)	Output Powers (dB)
200	39.62	4.37	14.85
300	40.97	4.38	16.76
400	41.90	4.38	18.10
500	42.61	4.39	19.14
600	43.18	4.39	19.99

To compare the co-propagating pumping at 1480 nm, the pump wavelength in Fig. 12 has been set to 1480 nm and other parameters are remained unchanged. Fig. 16 (a) and Fig. 16 (b) respectively show the gain and noise figure (NF) variation with pumping powers for co-propagating pumping at 1480 nm. As seen from these figures that the gains is slowly increasing with increase in pump powers but NF is slowly decreasing. The gain of the amplifier varies between 40.55 to 43.01 dB and the NF varies between 4.81 to 4.62 dB. The output signal level however, enhances with the values 21.61 to 26.92 dB. Table 3 shows the results.

Table 3: Gain, noise figure and output power for Co-propagating gains and noise parameters @1480 nm

Pump Power (mw)	Gains (dB)	Noise (dB)	Output Power (dB)
200	40.55	4.81	21.61
300	41.53	4.74	23.58
400	42.18	4.69	24.97
500	42.65	4.65	26.05
600	43.01	4.62	26.92

Fig. 16 (a) and Fig. 16 (b) respectively show the gain and noise figure (NF) variation with pumping powers for counter-propagating pumping at 980 nm. As seen from these figures that the gain is quite high and it increases from 39.74 to 43.26 dB whereas NF is slowly decreasing from 7.24 to 6.94 dB. The output signal level however, varies between 19.76 to 24.54 dB. Table 4 shows the results.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 16 (a) Gain and (b) Noise Figure variation for counting-propagating pumping @980 nm

Table 4: Gain, noise figure and output power for counting-propagating pumping @980 nm

Pump Power (mw)	Gains (dB)	Noise (dB)	Output Power (dB)
200	39.74	7.24	19.76
300	41.07	7.12	21.55
400	41.99	7.04	22.80
500	42.69	6.98	23.76
600	43.26	6.94	24.54

Fig. 17(a) and Fig. 17(b) respectively show the gain and noise figure (NF) variation with pumping powers for bi-propagating pumping at 980 nm. As seen from these figures that the gain is slowly increasing and NF almost constant with increase in pump powers. The gain of the amplifier is quite high and it varies between 43.21 to 46.55 dB and the NF varies only between 4.95 to 4.96 dB. The output signal level varies between 21.06 to 25.87 dB. Table 5 shows the results.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 17 (a)&(b) Bi-directional pumping @980 nm

Table 5 Gain, noise figure and output power for Bi-directional pumping @980 nm

Pump Power (mw)	Gains (dB)	Noise (dB)	Output Power (dB)
200	43.41	4.95	21.06
300	44.58	4.96	22.84
400	45.40	4.96	24.10
500	46.04	4.96	25.08
600	46.55	4.96	25.87

From the above results, it can be seen that the best performance is obtained by bi-directional pumping scheme as it gives the maximum value of output power for each case and in the case of co-propagating pumping at 980 the output power level is low and the NF is also increasing. However, co-propagating pumping at 1480 nm shows good results with moderate power and better noise performance. The performance comparison between co-directional, counter and bi-directional pumping schemes in terms of system parameters like BER and Q-factor is not studied which may be taken up as future work.

SYSTEM LAYOUT

The system layout for simulation in optisystem is shown in Fig. 18. A 16 channels WDM transmitter, dual port WDM analyzer, EDFA and BER analyzer are the key components used for 16 channels WDM system in the wavelength range between 1548 to 1560 nm with 0.75 nm channel spacing are used. Table 6 shows the WDM and EDFA parameters used for simulation.

Fig.18 Simulation Layout of 16 channels WDM System

Table 6:WDM and EDFA parameters

Parameters	Values
WDM transmitter frequency range	1548-1560 nm
Frequency spacing	0.75 nm
Number of WDM Channels	16
Bit rate, Modulation type	10 Gbps, NRZ
Optimized EDFA length	10m
EDFA core radius	1.2 μm
Er^{+3} ion density	$1.425 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-3}$
EDF numerical aperture	0.24

WDM SYSTEM DESIGN

The WDM system used for this analysis is designed using Optisystem 12.1 simulation software. In this simulation, 16 channels have been used at the input having wavelength range between 1548nm to 1560 nm with channel spacing of 0.75nm at a bit rate of 10 Gbps. Modulation type used is NRZ. Input power given to all the channels are taken between -20 dBm to -35dBm with 3 dBm variation. EDFA fiber amplifier is used to amplify the input signal which is pumped at different power levels at 980 nm pumping wavelength. The isolator is used at the input side in order to avoid any effects of ASE produced during amplification in WDM system. Isolator also prevents the information signal from travelling in the backward direction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the simulation model, pump power is varied from 100 to 400 mW and the input signal power is varied from -20 to -35dBm. Fig. 19 shows the output signal and noise spectra where an average gain of 38 dBm and a gain flatness of about 1.37dBm are achieved. The output power of about 22dBm and noise figure of about 8.04dBm are obtained. These values are taken from WDM analyzer when input signal power of -26 dBm and pump power of 300 mW are used at the optimized EDF length of 10m. The gain and noise figure variations across the complete frequency range for different pump powers are shown in Fig. 20(a) and Fig. 20(b) respectively at fixed input signal power of -26dBm. The same variations for different input powers are shown in Fig 21(a) and Fig.21(b) respectively at fixed pump power of 300 mW.

Fig. 19 Output signal and noise power variation at fixed input power -26dBm and 300mW Pump power

Fig. 20 (a)Gain variation of different pump power at fixed input power of -26dBm

Fig. 20 (b) Noise figure variation of different pump power a fixed input power of -26dBm

Fig. 21 (a) Gain variation for different input powers at fixed pump power of 300 mW

Fig.21 (b) Noise Figure variation for different input power at fixed pump power of 300 mW

Fig. 19 shows the output of 32 channels along with noise power. It is clear that all channels are having almost flat output and low noise. It is observed from Fig. 20(a) and Fig.20(b) that high average gain and low average noise figure are found at maximum pump power of 300 mW with gain flatness of about 1.34dBm and to achieve even better flatness (0.176dBm) both gain and noise figure has to be sacrificed a bit as shown in Table 7, where a pump power of 300 mW is sufficient. Fig.21(a) and Fig. 21(b) also show that high average gain and low average noise figure is found at pump power of 300 mW with gain flatness of about 1.34dBm and to achieve even better flatness (0.401dBm) in this case both gain and noise figure has to be sacrificed a bit again as shown in Table 7, where a input power of -31 dBm is required .These findings are useful for designing such system having predefined system requirements in terms of average gain, noise figure or gain flatness.

Table7: Gain and Noise value at different pump power and fixed input power of -26 dBm

Parameters	Input Power (dBm)				
	-20	-23	-26	-29	-32
Avg. Gain (dB)	33.56	36.33	38.77	40.69	41.98
Gain Flatness (\pm dB)	2.15	1.68	1.34	0.95	0.78
Avg. NF (dB)	10.43	9.56	9.09	8.68	8.52

Table 8: Gain and NF value at different input power and fixed pump power at 600 mW

Parameters	Pump Power (mW)			
	100	200	300	400
Avg. Gain (dB)	30.42	35.18	37.33	38.77
Gain Flatness (\pm dB)	2.68	1.883	1.55	1.37
Avg. NF (dB)	12.69	10.25	9.43	9.00

A 32 channels WDM system using EDFA in the wavelength range of 1546 to 1560 nm with channel spacing of 0.4 nm is designed and analysed. The gain flattening of EDFA in such system is achieved through EDFA’s pump power and input power variation. Results show that the gains are flattened within 43.6 ± 0.8 dB with noise figure about 7.38 dB at pump power of 600 mW and input power of -34 dBm using optimized erbium doped fiber of 6.2 m length. The performance evaluation in terms of BER, eye diagram and Q factor are necessary for complete system analysis with different bit rates. Due to some reasons these studies are not taken up so far and can be consider as future work. The performance analysis can be extended using more channels and higher bit rate cases of practical importance.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work some study on EDFA and WDM system has been carried out. The system layouts and analysis are made using Optisystem software.

As pumping of EDFA is one of the important design aspect in such study, hence various EDFA pumping schemes are analysed. The analysis is made for high pump power since operation of EDFA with such powers is advantageous in gain flattening of EDFA-WDM system. Output power in the range of 15-25dBm, and noise figure between 4.37-7.24dBm is achieved. Among the different pumping method bi-directional one has been found to have best performance.

A 16 channel EDFA-WDM system is analysed in C-band and gain flatness of such system has been analyzed by varying pump power between 100 to 400 mW and input signal power between -20 to -32dBm. The gains are flattened within 38.6 ± 1.34 dB for wavelength range 1548 nm to 1560 nm having noise figure less than 8.04 dB, using optimized EDFA of length 10 m.

The performance comparison between co-directional, counter and bi-directional pumping schemes in terms of system parameters like BER and Q-factor is not studied which may be taken up as future work

The performance evaluation in terms of BER, eye diagram and Q factor are necessary for complete system analysis with different bit rates. Due to some reasons these studies are not taken up so far and can be consider as future work. The performance analysis can be extended using more channels and higher bit rate cases of practical importance.

References

- [1] G. P. Agarwal, 'Fiber-Optic Communication Systems', John Wiley & Sons, New York, (1997).
- [2] P. C. Becker, N.A. Olsson and J.R. Simpson, 'Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifiers: Fundamentals and Technology', Academic Press, New York, (1999).
- [3] M.C. Paul, A. Pal, M. Pal, A. Dhar, R. Sen, S.K Bhandra and K. Dasgupta, 'Investigation of the optical gain and noise figure for multichannel amplification in EDFA under optimized pump condition', pp.407-412, Elsevier, (2007).
- [4] R.S Kaler and R. Kaler, 'Gain and Noise figure performance of Erbium doped fibre amplifiers (EDFA) and compact EDFAs', pp. 440-443, Elsevier, (2011).
- [5] F. Diana. B. Mahad and A. S. B. M. Supa, 'EDFA Gain Optimization for WDM System', ELEKTRIKA, VOL. 11, NO. 1, 34-37 (2009).
- [6] P. N. Sivakumar, A. Sangeetha, 'Gain Flatness of EDFA in WDM Systems', International conference on Communication and Signal Processing, April 3-5, 2013, India, IEEE, 713-716.
- [7] S. Semmalar, Poonkuzhali, P.Devi, 'Optimized Gain EDFA of different Lengths with aninfluence of Pump Power', IEEE, ICECCT- 2011.
- [8] M. A Othman, M. M. Ismail, H.A. Sulaiman, M.H. Misran, M. A. M Said, 'EDFA-WDM optical network analysis', International Journal of Electronics and Computer Science Engineering, 1894-1904, 2012.
- [9] D. Verma and S. Meena, 'Flattening the Gain in 16 Channel EDFA-WDM System By Gain Flattening Filter', Sixth International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Communication Networks, IEEE,174-177, 2014.
- [10] H. Ju, A. Uskov et al, 'Effects of two photon absorption on carrier dynamics in Quantum-dot optical amplifiers', Appl. Phy. B, 82, pp. 615-620 (2006).
- [11] K. Tajima et al, 'Semiconductor nonlinearities for ultrafast all optical gating', Measurement Science and Technology, 13, pp. 1692-1697 (2001).
- [12] J. Mendoza-Alvarez et al., 'Analysis of depletion edge transition lightwave modulators', J. Lightwave Technol., 6, pp. 793-807 (1988).
- [13] P. C. Becker, N.A. Olsson and J.R. Simpson, 'Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifiers: Fundamentals and Technology', Academic Press, New York, (1999).
- [14] C. Headley and G.P. Agarwal, "Raman Amplification in Fiber Optical Communication Systems", Elsevier Academic Press, (2005).
- [15] M.N. Islam, 'Raman Amplifiers for Telecommunications 1, Physical Principles', Springer, (2004).
- [16] M.AMalek and A. Malekmohammadi], 'Limitation in the intrinsic method of EDFA gain optimization for 32X10 Gbps WDM systems', Elsevier, (2011).

- [17] R. Vijaya and R. Deepa, ‘Influence of bidirectional pumping in high-power EDFA on single-channel, Multichannel and pulsed signal amplification’, Elsevier, pp. 20-26 (2008).
- [18] F. Vasile and P. Schioppa, ‘The EDFA Performance with gain versus pump power’, IEEE Semiconductor Conference, vol. 1, (2004).
- [19] R. F. Souza, S. Milo, M.B.C. Silva, E. Conforti and C. Bordonalli, ‘An EDFA Theoretical Analysis Considering Different Configuration and Pumping Wavelengths’, IEEE Microwave and Optoelectronics Conference, vol. 1, pp. 105-110(2003).
- [20] A.C. Cokrak and A. Altuncu, “Gain and Noise Figure Performance of Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifiers”, Journal of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, vol. 4, pp. 1111-1122(2004).
- [21] S. Raghavan, J Downie, J Hurley, Y. Mauro and M. Sauer, “Fiber Attributes & Dispersion Compensation Strategies in Optical Communication Systems”, International conference on Fiber Optics and Photonics, (2008).